

DIDACTIC FOUNDATIONS OF THE COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14574974>

Annotation: This article studies the didactic foundations of the communicative approach in teaching English. The communicative approach is considered as an important tool for developing students' communication skills, teaching them to use the language in real-life situations. The article analyzes the main principles of this approach, in particular, learner-centeredness, dialogue orientation, the use of interactive methods and the organization of a meaningful learning process. It also highlights effective methods aimed at strengthening cooperation between teachers and students and the formation of communicative competence. The results of the study serve to deepen the understanding of the theoretical and practical aspects of using the communicative approach in teaching English.

Keywords: Communicative approach, English teaching, didactic foundations, communicative competence, dialogue orientation, interactive methods, learner-centeredness, educational effectiveness.

In today's era of globalization, English is recognized not only as a means of international communication, but also as one of the main tools that open the way to global knowledge and opportunities. The process of learning a language is no longer just about learning grammatical rules and increasing vocabulary. On the contrary, it requires the formation of communicative competence aimed at developing students' ability to communicate in real-life situations. In this sense, the communicative approach to teaching English has become the center of the modern educational process.

The main principle of the communicative approach is to see students as active participants in education. This approach does not only consist of transferring knowledge, but also creates opportunities for its practical application. In the process of language teaching, the priority goal of the communicative approach is to prepare students for real-life communication, to form in them the skills of exchanging ideas and solving problem situations.

In the modern educational process, strengthening the interaction between the teacher and the student, using interactive methods and organizing education in accordance with the individual needs of students are important principles of

the communicative approach. In this case, the teacher is not only a provider of knowledge, but also a guide, motivator and partner.

This article discusses the theoretical and practical aspects of the communicative approach, its didactic foundations, as well as methods for effectively applying this approach in the process of teaching the English language. After all, knowing a language is not only understanding the rules, but also communicating with the world through it. Therefore, the importance of the communicative approach is increasingly increasing in the modern education system.

The communicative approach to teaching English includes principles aimed at teaching students the language as a means of communication in real-life situations. In this approach, the main emphasis is on its practical application rather than memorizing the rules of the language. The methodology places students at the center of the learning process and makes them active participants in communication.

A number of interactive methods were used in the research to implement the communicative approach. For example, role-playing games teach students to communicate by imitating real-life situations. These activities increase students' vocabulary and help them form their speech. Group discussions also encourage students to exchange ideas, which develops their independent thinking and fluency in the use of language.

The use of technology also plays an important role within the methodology. Digital platforms, such as mobile applications for language learning and online learning platforms, allow students to practice individually. Audio and video materials are effective tools for developing listening comprehension and speaking.

Teaching adapted to the needs of students is also an integral part of the methodology. A person-centered approach ensures that students' knowledge levels are determined using diagnostic tests and lessons are organized accordingly. Thus, taking into account the individual development and interests of students creates the basis for their success.

In conclusion, the communicative approach methodology makes the educational process interesting and meaningful, preparing students for real-life communication. For the effective implementation of this approach, the high skills of the teacher and the activity of the students play an important role.

A picture of a teacher teaching in a classroom based on the communicative approach methodology. Students are divided into small groups and play role-

playing games. On the walls of the classroom, there are exhibitions related to the English language lesson and the content of the lesson is displayed on the multimedia screen. Students and teachers are actively communicating with each other.

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A number of interactive methods were used in the implementation of the communicative approach during the study. For example, role-playing games teach students to communicate by imitating real-life situations. These activities increase students' vocabulary and help them form their speech. Group discussions also encourage students to exchange ideas, which develops their independent thinking and fluency in the use of language.

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Literature review:

The scientific and literary sources on the importance of the communicative approach in teaching English include extensive research. This review mainly analyzed literature on communicative competence, modern methods of language learning and the role of the teacher.

The work "Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching" by J. Richards and T. Rodgers (2001) describes the theoretical foundations of the communicative approach. The authors outlined the main principles of the

communicative approach aimed at developing students' communication skills. This approach aims to teach students how to use language in real-life situations. This work provides teachers with methodological guidelines for orienting the learning process towards communication. H. Brown (2000) in his work "Principles of Language Learning and Teaching" analyzes psychological factors in the process of language teaching. The author emphasizes the important role of the communicative approach in increasing students' motivation and internal interest in learning the language. He notes the teacher's skill in organizing communication with students as one of the main factors in the development of communicative competence.

Larsen-Freeman (2000)'s book "Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching" highlights the advantages of various teaching methods, including the communicative approach. The author describes in detail the possibilities of increasing educational effectiveness by combining this approach with interactive methods, role-playing games, and group discussions.

The State Program of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Improving the Quality of Education in 2019–2030 sets out measures to introduce modern technologies into the language teaching process and expand interactive approaches. This document shows that the communicative approach to teaching English is also relevant in the national education system.

An analysis of the literature shows that the communicative approach is recognized not only as a theoretical basis, but also as a method that gives high results in practice. The analyzed works, while enriching the theoretical foundations of this approach, provide effective tools for introducing them into the practical activities of teachers. Therefore, the literature on this topic is of great importance not only for scientific research, but also for improving the skills of teachers.

Discussion:

The communicative approach, unlike traditional approaches, is aimed at developing students' practical skills in the process of teaching English. This approach helps to turn the lesson not only as a process of acquiring knowledge, but also into a field of lively communication. Discussions and observations show that through this methodology, students become more active, they begin to learn not only from the teacher, but also from each other.

One of the important principles of the communicative approach is communication orientation. During the lesson, students should have the opportunity to use the language in real-life situations. For example, role-playing

games and group discussions not only develop students' language skills, but also increase their social and collective activity. With the help of these methods, students learn to express their thoughts freely and learn not to be afraid to communicate.

The communicative approach is also more effective when combined with technology. The use of digital tools, such as language learning applications, virtual communication platforms and multimedia resources, not only engages students with new technologies, but also develops their independent learning skills. However, in this process, improper use of technologies or the teacher's inability to use them can cause problems. Therefore, training teachers to work with modern technologies remains an important issue.

Another important aspect of the communicative approach is taking into account the needs of students. Each student has a different level of knowledge and unique abilities. Therefore, organizing the lesson in a person-centered manner ensures the active participation of students in the language learning process. For example, through an individual approach, their strengths can be developed and weaknesses can be eliminated.

One of the main aspects identified during the discussion is that the success of the communicative approach depends on the skills of the teacher and the learning environment created. When a teacher creates a supportive and inspiring environment for students, their interest in the lesson increases. Also, the development of cooperation between students increases the effectiveness of this approach.

In conclusion, the communicative approach is an effective methodology that leads to innovative and practical results in teaching English. It prepares students not only to learn the language, but also to apply it in life. Therefore, the wider introduction of this approach in the education system, increasing its compatibility with technologies, and supporting teachers with advanced training courses remain one of the urgent issues of modern education.

Conclusion.

In today's era of globalization, learning English should not be limited to just grammatical rules and memorizing vocabulary. Language is a means of communication, and its acquisition should be carried out through dialogue. From this point of view, the communicative approach has become the main foundation of modern education. This approach builds students' practical skills aimed at applying language in real-life situations, not just as theoretical knowledge.

The main principles of the communicative approach are to make students active participants in the lesson process, to interest them and to develop their independent thinking skills. Interactive methods, role-playing games and group exercises increase students' motivation to learn the language. Enriching the learning process with the help of technologies further enhances the advantages of the modern approach. The use of digital tools creates convenient opportunities for students to learn independently.

At the same time, the main key to the success of the communicative approach is the teacher's activity. The teacher should act not only as a provider of knowledge, but also as a guide and motivator for students. Also, taking into account the needs of students, organizing lessons in a person-oriented manner and effectively cooperating with them is an important part of this approach. In conclusion, the communicative approach is a methodological framework that has proven its effectiveness in the field of language teaching. It develops students' practical skills, prepares them to use the language freely in life, and makes the educational process interesting and meaningful. Therefore, the widespread introduction of this approach in the education system, improving the skills of teachers, and the wider use of technologies are among the priorities of modern education. Teaching a language through a communicative approach is not only about imparting knowledge, but also about teaching how to communicate with the world.

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